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ABSTRACTS

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Deep Learning-Based Antibiotic Resistance Prediction Modelling

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Abstract: Antibiotic resistance poses a global health challenge, necessitating precise and timely predictive strategies. This research article underscores the urgency for innovative methodologies to address resistance patterns effectively. The abstract presents a groundbreaking deep-learning model for forecasting antibiotic resistance in bacterial strains. Leveraging neural networks, the model utilizes diverse genomic features, offering a robust tool for healthcare professionals.

Methodology: The method employs a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to autonomously extract hierarchical representations from genomic data. Processes involving bacterial isolates' genomic sequences undergo multiple layers of CNN processing, capturing patterns pivotal to antibiotic resistance. Trained on a curated dataset spanning bacterial species and antibiotics, the model ensures adaptability across diverse ecosystems. Key features, including handling large-scale genomic data and providing swift, accurate predictions for multiple antibiotics, highlight the dynamic learning framework's adaptability to emerging resistance patterns. The evaluation demonstrates the model's superiority, emphasizing accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity across bacterial strains and antibiotics. Visualization techniques enhance interpretability, revealing genomic elements influencing resistance predictions.

Result: the deep learning-based model is a valuable tool for guiding antibiotic prescriptions, optimizing treatments, and contributing to the global fight against antibiotic resistance. As genomic sequencing advances, the model stands as a scalable solution, supporting evidence-based decision-making in clinical and public health settings.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network, Genomic sequencing, Predictive model, Healthcare, Microbial ecosystems, Resistance patterns, Evidence-based decision-making.

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